

A Small Change Makes a Big Difference: Adoption of Seed Biodiversity and Multiplication

REVIVING THE TRADITIONAL MILLET, PULSES AND OILSEED-BASED
BIODIVERSE AGRICULTURAL SYSTEM IN BIHAR AND WEST BENGAL

STORIES FROM THE GROUND
(With videos from the field)

All stories are taken from project sites under
FAO-ITPGRFA IV Cycle For INDIA
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ABOUT PAIRVI

PAIRVI (Public Advocacy Initiative for Rights and Values in India) is a non-profit organization that was formed in 1998 and registered under Section 25 of the Indian Companies Act, 1956. The lobbying organization is a capacity building and guiding organization that works with grassroots organizations and community-based groups for their consistent development and sustainability. Apart from this, there is also a lot of vocal work on climate change, food sovereignty and protection of people rights. The primary constituency of PAIRVI is specific attention to the most marginalized and the most vulnerable populations across all sections of the society. It advocates rights-based approach to development. It also engages with UN agencies working on sustainable development and environment including *United Nations General Assembly, High Level Political Forum on SDGs, United Nations Environment, and UN Economic and Social Commission for Asia and Pacific*. PAIRVI is an active member of the Asia Pacific Regional CSOs Engagement Mechanism on Agenda 2030.

FAO-ITPGR PROJECT

India is second largest rice producing country of the world with about 40 m hectare area under rice cultivation. About 30% of i.e. 12 million ha of this area is left fallow during the following Rabi (post-rainy) season. Of the total rice fallow area about 82% lies in the Central and Eastern Indian states of Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, and West Bengal. India is deficit in pulses and imports 2-3 mtr to meet the domestic pulses demand. Despite the government's efforts in the past 8 years to strengthen seed production and distribution, there is a shortage of 50,000 tonnes of seeds of pulse.

This project aims at improving pulses, oilseeds and millets biodiversity in rice fallow areas of tribal belts of Central and East Indian states to bring resilience in the farming practice provide livelihood support and enhance nutritional level of the tribal population. The careful selection of pulses for cultivation in rice fallow areas of this tribal rich belt offers opportunities for an additional crop for them utilising the moisture that the soil retains post monsoon and thereby offers food and nutritional security.

**PROJECT AREA: BIHAR
(DISTRICT- JAMUI, BLOCK- CHAKAI, VILLAGES-BAREDIH,
CHIHARA, BADLHADIH, BASHARA, SIRSI):**

The remote hilly and plateau areas falling under **Chakai** block in **Jamui district of Bihar** were selected by the lobbying agency. This difficult area is surrounded by mountains and forests. Being inaccessible, the area was once a haven for Naxalites. The development oriented schemes of the Central and State Governments could not reach the tribal of the region. As a result, the tribal community was struggling with problems like education, health, unemployment, migration, etc.

Based on the geography and climatic conditions field trials of different varieties of pulses: Pigeon pea, Black gram, Groundnut, Green gram, Cow pea, Kudrum (*Hibiscus cannabinus*), Ghagra (*Vigna sinensis*), Horseshoe gram, Gram, Khesari, Little Pea (*Pisum sativum*), Red

lentil and oil seeds: White sesame, Black sesame, Red sesame, Niger, Mustard, Linseed and Sunflower have been successfully carried out in the project area. Field Trials carried out on the farms of 78 tribal farmers who in turn received hands on training to carry out farm-trials for on-farm conservation and varietal selection. Through participatory variety selection phenotypes of the crops have been documented, seeds collected and conserved off-farms in the 5 community seed banks established under the project.

SUCCESS STORIES

STORY OF BRICK KILN LABOURERS WHO ARE NOW PROUD OWNERS OF ARHAR FIELDS

It's a rousing story of such farmers who were once forced to feed the family by doing wage work in the brick kiln. **Tuka Besra and Pudi Soren** of **village Sirsia** described that before joining the organization, they were daily wage labourers working in a brick kiln. Despite their own fields, they were hand to mouth on what they earned. They were marginal farmers growing only one crop i.e. rice during rainy season. They used to buy seeds of pulses from the market at a cost, yet were not able to meet both the ends. Those seeds were not high yielding and reliable. Left with no other option, they had to work as daily wagers and whatever they used to earn, the family was somehow fed with. They were only getting to eat simple food, mostly rice with potato curry and sometimes with water only, even oil and spices were luxury for them. PAIRVI came up as a blessing for these poor fellows. After joining the organization PAIRVI, there is a big change in their life. This projected has assisted these farmers to grow pulses and oilseeds crops in four times ensuring year-round food security. They get seeds for maize, arhar, mustard and chana from the seed bank. The beneficiary of the passbook linked to the seed bank gets 3 to 4 kg of pulses seeds per family. These seeds are traditional varieties (desi), yet give a better yield of 30-35 kg. The oilseeds and pulses (like moong, arhar, chana, mustard, summer moong, summer urad) in barren land and rice fallow area has not only given an opportunity to these farmers for extra income but has also improved the protein intake of the villagers. The most important aspect is that these

farmers are never encouraged to use chemical fertilizers; they are using cow dung only as manure in their fields, thus ensuring PURE ORGANIC FARMING. There has been a huge impact on the livelihood of the tribal community of this region. Pudi Soren testified that today the crops of pulses and oilseeds are flourishing in their fields. Some vegetables are also grown. Now they have also started getting sesame seeds and mustard seeds. And they are using these oils for their domestic use only. They are not selling but it has reduced the dependency on market, creating self-sufficiency among these tribal people. Soren's family is prospering for last two years and they are now well pleased that they never have to go back to brick kilns for wages. Inspired by their success, there was also a positive change in the lives of other villagers. They are also becoming a part of the change by getting associated with the Project.

Hindi Language:

इट के भट्टे में काम करने वाले मजदूरों के खेत में लहलाती अरहर की फसल तुका बेसरा (सिरसिया) एवं पूदी सोरेन (सिरसिया):

इस project से ग्रामीणों में, प्रोटीन intake में काफी सुधार हुआ है, इनके livelihood पर व्यापक प्रभाव हुआ है एक सीजन में passbook के लाभार्थी को 3 से 4 kg दाल प्रति परिवार उपलब्ध हो पाती है Arhar की दाल की उन्नत किस्मों (रतन)के साथ कुछ desi किस्मों के बीज भी क्षेत्र में बांटे गए हैं। **तुका बेसरा (सिरसिया) एवं पूदी सोरेन (सिरसिया)** ने बताया, प्रोजेक्ट से पूर्व, वे चूंकि ज्यादातर ईट के भट्टे पर काम करने वाले दिहाड़ी मजदूर हैं, इसलिए आलू की करी के साथ ही ज्यादातर खाना खाते थे, जो दिहाड़ी से कमाते थे उससे थोड़ा मिर्ची मसाला और तेल लेकर आते थे। लेकिन, आज इनके खेत में दलहन और तिलहन लहरा रहा है। इनके यहां तिल और सरसों भी होने लगा है, जिसका ये तेल निकलवा के आते हैं। Arhar इनकी बहुत अच्छी होती है। **तुका बेसरा (सिरसिया)** अब इट के भट्टे पर दिहाड़ी मजदूरी करने नहीं जाता, इसके बजाय खेती में जुड़ गया है। पूरे साल season के अनुसार dalhan और tilhan लगाता है kuch सब्जियां भी कर लेता है। आगे उसने सोचा है की सभी आसपास के लोग मिलकर सरसों पिलाई एवं dalhan की छोटी मिल लगाया जाए। जिसके लिए वो प्रयासरत है। **सिरसिया गाँव के तुका बेसरा एवं पूदी सोरेन के** जीवन में आये बदलाव का असर पास के लगते गाँव बसहरा में भी पड़ा है जिसके चलते बसहरा गाँव के किसानों -कामु यादव (बसहरा), जानकी देवी (बसहरा), लक्ष्मण यादव (बसहरा), घटियानी से मनोज टुडू, बारीडीह से जीवा सोरेन के जीवन में बदलाव आया है।

Video Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bWpZD-5j6ws>

SUCCESSFUL REVIVAL OF LOTNI

Lotni, a variety of black mustard which was completely lost in the area, was successfully revived by the indefatigable spirit of PAIRVI. **Janaki Devi** from **Bashara village** was the first one to plant this traditional variety in her farm in 2020. Though the production that year was only 5kg, yet Janaki Devi preferred it over the other hybrid varieties of mustard. She felt nostalgic while quoting that this (variety) was what she used to plant and eat in her parents' house, but with time it was lost. She got a yield of 8 kg in the year 2021. The traditional variety Lotni, known for its strong flavour, density, pungent aroma and high smoke point, has been also revived by **Durari Devi, Sunita Hansda and Sheila Murmu of Ghatiyani village**. Before this project, they used to buy mustard oil from the nearby grocery stores. Being adulterated, it was cheap and hazardous for the health. Today these proud producers of

lotni are quite happy as they consume pure and their own produced mustard oil for their domestic use. Low production of the oil doesn't seem to bother Janaki Devi as she quoted- "production may be less, but we eat is desi and pure oil today."

The residents of this area, currently 8 women, have created a female Santhal Samuh of those who extract lotni and yellow mustard oil and link it to the market. The group is still unregistered, yet this variety is appreciated and brought by the people from far and wide. Recently, their goods were kept at the International Trade Fair of SIAL organized by the Bhoomika Project at Pragati Maidan. They were praised by one and all for their ragi flour (finger millet), white maize flour (corn meal) and lotni oil. This has cheered up the women of Ghatiyani and Bashara Village.

Hindi Language:

जानकी देवी ने किया लौटनी-किस्म का संरक्षण

यह प्रोजेक्ट देसी किस्मों के संरक्षण में काम कर रहा है इसके चलते लौटनी, जो सरसों कि एक किस्म है, को क्षेत्र में बचाया गया है। लौटनी किस्म, क्षेत्र में से विलुप्त हो गयी थी जिसको इस प्रोजेक्ट में संरक्षित किया गया।

जानकी देवी, बसहरा गाँव से है इन्होंने पहली बार 2020 में लौटनी किस्म को अपने खेत में लगाया था। उस साल उत्पादन 5kg रहा लेकिन यह किस्म जानकी देवी को संकरित किस्म से ज्यादा पसंद है क्योंकि उसका कहना है की उसके माता-पिता के घर वह यही लगाती और खाती थी लेकिन समय के साथ सब बीज समाप्त हो गया। 2021 में लौटनी किस्म का उत्पादन इसके पास 8 kg है। क्षेत्र में परम्परागत किस्म लौटनी को गाँव के किसानों ने इसके गाढ़े तेल के कारण एवं तीखी गंध के कारण पुनः लगाना प्रारम्भ कर दिया है इसमें **दुलारी देवी (घटियानी)**, **सुनीता हांसदा (घटियानी)**, **शीला मुर्मू (घटियानी)** है। यह सभी प्रोजेक्ट से पहले सरसों के तेल के लिए गाँव के किराना स्टोर से, सरसों का तेल लेकर आती थी, जो सस्ता होने के चलते काफी मिलावट पूर्ण होता था जिससे इनके स्वास्थ्य पर भी बुरा प्रभाव पड़ता था। आज जब ना केवल शुद्ध सरसों का तेल इनके पास है बल्कि यह देसी सरसों का तेल है जिस पर **जानकी देवी** यह बोलती है की **"उत्पादन भले ही कम हो, लेकिन हम देसी और शुद्ध तेल खाते हैं आज"**।

लौटनी-किस्म का तेल निकालकर क्षेत्र के निवासियों, जिसमें अभी 8 महिलाएँ हैं, ने एक महिला संधाल samuh बनाया है। जिसमें लौटनी एवं पीली सरसों का तेल निकालकर उसे मार्केट से लिंक करने का काम किया है। अभी यह group unregistered है। फिर भी lotni वैरायटी के इस तेल को लेने दूर-दूर

से लोग आते हैं। हाल ही में इनके बनाए सामान को Bhoomika project द्वारा आयोजित SIAL के अंतर्राष्ट्रीय व्यापार मेले में, प्रगति मैदान में रखा गया। जहाँ लोगो ने इनके रागी के आटे, सफेद भुट्टे के आटे और लोटनी के तेल को खूब सराह। इससे घटियानी और बसहरा गाँव की महिलाओं में उत्साह है।

Video Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YEh0l7Y7Pcg&t=73s>

MIXED CULTIVATION OF GRAM, PEAS AND BARLEY

Mixed crops of grams, pears and barley can produce stable yields for protein production; with the risk of yield loss being reduced. No one used to cultivate green peas in the area due to lack of information about this crop in the new generation. The lobbyists met the farmers and scientists of **KVK (Krishi Vigyan Kendra)** and found that under mixed farming in the area, peas with gram, barley were planted. For the trial in the farm of Hareram Yadav and Tek Narayan, three rows of barley were kept and two rows of peas were given in the middle. This has served as an excellent combination.

In the very first trial, a total produce of 8 kg of peas from **Hareram Yadav** and **Teknarayan** fields and 4 kg of barley from Hareram Yadav's field was received. This encouraged the other farmers a lot. As a result, in 2021, Janaki Devi, Rajender Yadav, Pradeep Yadav, Shanti Hembram, Munni Devi Hembram also opted for mixed farming. A good yield of 35kg of peas was cultivated in the year 2021. Munni Devi Hembram felt proud while quoting, "Now we grow peas at home; earlier we could not buy peas as they cost upto Rs 40-70/kg." Barley was first introduced in the fields of Tek Narayan, Hareram, Bablu Soren, Rajender Yadav; Surajmuni Hembram of Ghatiyani. Sirsia and Basehra villages also planted barley in 2021, and received a good yield of 25 kg of barley. Now the people of the village mainly prepare the dish "Puha" made of barley flour. Peas and barley are mostly cultivated for the domestic use in this area. This practice has enhanced the nutritional requirements of the villagers. In the paddy fallow area, gram also grows with light moisture along with the peas and barley, which is an excellent source of protein as well as iron. According to Hareram, Pradeep Yadav, Teknarayan, Pammu Yadav, Shanti Hembram (Sirsia), Munni Hembram (Sirsia), the area of gram has reached 10 sacks per farmer, which was earlier limited to 2-4 sacks per

farmer. The limit of seeds has also increased from 2 -3 kg per season to 4-5kg/season. Along with this, these farmers also planted corn crops, horse gram, lentils, sesame, and moong.

Munni Hembram of Sirsia village told, "We had forgotten ragi, now ragi has become an indispensable part of my farm". Earlier, despite of their own land, they used to do labour work in the hotel. Most of the women used to go to work in the brick kiln. They were dependent on the market for vegetables, oil, spices, pulses, oilseeds and seeds throughout the year. They used to grow paddy and in the winter season, wheat was grown only in the irrigated part. They had to buy wheat and rice grains from the market for 2-3 months in a year. Under this project, even during the period of Covid Epidemic, they got seeds of vegetables, pulses, oilseeds, maize, barley, ragi, due to which the crop came in three months and this enabled them to get the food items of our daily life. The farmers are having seed saving account and passbook and CSB committee maintain the registered book. The farmers are returning double than what they received from bank. They did not face any problem in daily food items during the second wave of Covid as they were not dependent upon the market. 100 passbooks have been registered with the community seed bank so far and 120 KGB seeds have been distributed till date.

Tekrayan of Basehra village told that the Ghagra (*Xanthium strumarium*), white and red Roselle (*coccinia grandis*) had completely disappeared in the area and seeds were not available in the market but this project has given life to these crops again.

Hindi Language:

हरेराम यादव और टेकनारायण ने किया क्षेत्र में चना, मटर और जौ की मिश्रित खेती से पैदावार

क्षेत्र में हरे मटर की खेती कोई नहीं करता था, नयी पीढ़ी के लोगों में इस फसल को लेकर जानकारी का अभाव था। पैरवी ने किसानों से और KVK के वैज्ञानिकों से मिलकर पाया कि क्षेत्र में मिश्रित खेती के तहत चना, जौ के साथ मटर लगाया जाए। **हरेराम यादव और टेकनारायण के यंहा** ट्रायल farm में, तीन रो Jou की रखी गई और दो रो matar की बीच-बीच में दी गयी। इससे मटर और जौ दोनों ही काफी अच्छी हुयी। 2020 में लगाए गए ट्रायल प्लाट से **हरेराम यादव और टेकनारायण** के यंहा पहली बार 8 kg मटर निकला और **हरेराम यादव** के यंहा से ट्रायल प्लाट से **जौ** 4 kg निकला था। इसे देख के 2021 में अन्य किसानों ने जिसमें जानकीदेवी, राजेंदर यादव, प्रदीप यादव, शांति हेम्ब्रम, मुन्नी देवी हेम्ब्रम ने भी लगाया। 2021 में मटर 35 kg मटर लेगा निकलेगा। **मुन्नी देवी हेम्ब्रम** का कहना है की **"अब मटर की सब्जी घर में ही पैदा कर लेते हैं, पहले मटर महंगा होने के चलते हम खरीद नहीं पाते थे 40 -70 रुपए तक इस के भाव हो जाते हैं इतना महंगी सब्जी कैसे खाते हम"**। Jou को पहली बार क्षेत्र में introduce किया गया था। घटियानी, सिरसिया, बसेहरा गाँव के टेकरायण, हरेराम, बबलू सोरेन, राजेंदर यादव, सूरजमुनि हेम्ब्रम ने 2021 में जौ लगाया, जिसका उत्पादन 25 kg होगा। अब गाँव के लोग, जौ का आटा बना के बनेमुख्य रूप से पकवान "पुआ" बनाते हैं। क्षेत्र के लोग अब matar और jou लगा रहें हैं जितना भी matar होता है वे लोग अभी घर में उपयोग लेते हैं। इसके साथ ही धान परती क्षेत्र में चना हल्की नमी के साथ भी उग जाता है जो प्रोटीन के साथ-साथ आयरन का भी अच्छा source है। चने की फसल पर प्रोजेक्ट पर विशेष ध्यान दिया गया। हरेराम, प्रदीप यादव, टेकनारायण, पम्मू यादव, शांति हेम्ब्रम (सिरसिया), मुन्नी हेम्ब्रम (सिरसिया) के यंहा अब चना का रकबा 10 कठ्ठा प्रति किसान तक पहुंच गया है जो पहले 2 कठ्ठा -4 कठ्ठा तक सिमित था। अब 4-5 kg चना प्रति सीजन उपलब्ध हो जाता है जो पहले 2 -3 kg प्रति season उपलब्ध था। इसके साथ-साथ इन किसानों ने भुट्टा, kulthi, मसूर, तिल, मूंग की फसलों को भी लगाया गया। रागी, जो पूरी तरह से क्षेत्र में से विलुप्त हो गयी थी, प्रोजेक्ट में बाहर के aadivasi गाँव से बीज लाया गया। सिरसिया गाँव की **मुन्नी**

हेमन्त्रम का कहना है की "रागी को हम भूल चुके थे अब रागी मेरे खेत का हिस्सा है"। हरेराम जी बताते है की कोविड की पहली लहर में हमारे यंहा से शहरो में मजदूरी करने के लिए जो लोग जाते थे, जो होटल में लेबर का कार्य करते थे और जो ज्यादातर महिलाये ईट के भट्टे में मजदूरी करने जाती थी सबका काम बंद हो गया था। हम अपनी जमीं होते हुए भी पूरे सालभर सब्जी, तेल, मसाला, दलहन, तिलहन और बीज के लिए बाजार पर निर्भर थे और covid में बाजार बंद थे। हम सब लोग केवल धान उगाते थे जिससे केवल 6 माह का गुजरा हो पता था। और सर्दी के मौसम में केवल सिचाई वाले भाग में गेहू उगाते थे। जिससे 2 माह का गेहू निकलता था। वर्ष में 2-3 माह के लिए गेहू एवं चावल का दाना हम बाजार से खरीदते थे। कोविड के समय इस प्रोजेक्ट से हमें सब्जी, तेल, दलहन, तिलहन, मक्का, जौ, रागी का बीज मिला, जिससे तीन माह में ही फसल आ गयी और इससे हमारे दैनिक जीवन की खाने की चीजे मिल पायी। इसमें से भी हमने कुछ बीज सामुदायिक बीज बैंक में जमा करवाया ताकि यह पुनः हमें मिल जाये और यह चेन इसी प्रकार चलती रही। इसका फायदा हमें दूसरी कोविड की लहर में हुआ, बाजार पर निर्भरता काम होने से हमे खाने की दैनिक चीजों में कोई खास परेशानी नहीं हुयी। सामुदायिक बीज बैंक से इस प्रोजेक्ट से अब तक 100 पासबुक दी गयी है जिनके द्वारा 120 KGबीजों का वितरण किया गया है। बसेहरा गाँव के टेकरायण जी ने बताया की क्षेत्र मे घाघरा, सफेद और लाल kudrum पूरी तरह से लुप्त हो गयी थी और बाजार मे इसका बीज भी नहीं मिलता है, पैरवी के इस प्रोजेक्ट से इन फसलों को पुनः जीवन मिला है।

Video Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rdiVt0PMHNg>

PROJECT AREA: WEST BENGAL (DISTRICT- DHUPJHORA, MURTI):

Tribal farmers earn double from indigenous pulses

Introduction

"Desi jinish er ato demand hobe ami kokhono bhabi nai". I never ever thought that our indigenous pulse would be so high in demand"- Kamini Oraon.

A humble tribal women Kamini Oraon, aged 42 of Pashim Batabari village, Matiali BLock, Jalpaiguri district traditionally grow pulses like arhar, kala dal, and other indigenous variety crops like desi Jute, rai sag (green leafy veg) at her farm land helping her father and brother in farming from her tender age. Now she is married with two children but stay with her husband at her father's home with separate kitchen.

Pic 1: Kamini Oraon and his brother Mithun Oraon

Background

After her father's death now it's her brother and she continue farming at their father's agriculture land. They collectively own 1.47 ha of land of which .13 ha is under beetle nut plantation and rest 1.34 ha covers with paddy during kharif, jute during pre-kharif and vegetables like cauliflower, cabbage, tomato, cucumber, beans during Rabi season.

Apart she also cultivates kalo dal (Urad Dal), sim (Flat lima bean), misti kumra (sweet pumpkin), holud (turmeric), rosun (garlic) along with her brother.

But the biggest threat she encounters in agriculture are open grazing during rabi and pre kharif season, bird attack during fruiting and if saved from animal and bird many times the crop gets damaged from insect and finally the price fluctuation of the produce.

Moreover, during high pest and insect attack they has depended on chemical medicine to get rid of. Now when final cost of production is calculated with hybrid seed and chemical medicine application, they find the margin of profit at per / minimum or most of the time loss.

Tired of the such volatile situation in the agriculture sector she decided to take another side income source where she has been working from last two years in a private tea garden as casual labour to receive a range of fort nightly income every month. To support the income of the family her husband has to migrate in the states like Kerala, Sikkim, Punjab and few other states as construction and agriculture labour.

Crux

On such situation Community Seed Bank brings a ray of opportunity or scope to revisit agriculture from different angle. Kamini Oraon and her brother Mithun Oraon were traditional farmers. This means they used to follow traditional system of agriculture since their birth along with their father. Traditionally they used to grow crops with indigenous variety seed which they used to preserve at home and then reuse next year.

They used to grow paddy with indigenous variety seeds like Biru for rice, Kalonuniya for rice, Bochi for Staffed rice, Dudhkolom for puffed rice, tulai panji for dessert. But the only problem with those variety were that their yield ranged 5 to 8 Mon per bigha.

But in the recent past plenty of rice variety have arrived in market which at the lowest produce 14 – 15 mon per bigha. That naturally attracted them to adopt those new hybrid variety. And by this process the indigenous variety got aloof from their house. In the recent past due to good production of paddy from the improved variety paddy seed not only quench the hunger of the family but also fetch good money from sale. But on the hinge side as per reflection of Kamini, they also need to apply a good range of chemical spray which costs high in price and at the same time bad for the soil and even for other health of related organism includes we human.

“One of the problems, we are facing in agriculture is that we are slowly but obviously getting dependent on the fertilizer shop. It was only during covid -19 lock down we could realize that how much we got depended on others. Hybrid seed, chemical fertilizer, chemical insecticide and pesticide and even chemical weedicide. During lock down we could hardly access any shop for all the input we got accustomed to.

But only then the Community Seed Bank extended its support with seed at homestead and at the same time understood the power of indigenous variety of seeds and crops our father and fore father used to cultivate.” – Kamini Oraon.

It is only from previous year 2021, they initiated emphasizing on preserving our indigenous variety seed of which turmeric, garlic, potato, urad dal, local jute, with special emphasis. Traditionally they used to preserve the seed after harvest by alternate 10 – 15 days sun dry and packing in cotton cloth.

Role of Community Seed Bank in Kamini's profit

According to Kamini CSB has supported at the crucial time with seed and legitimate suggestion on farming. The very first thing they learned the importance of organic produce. When all the shops were closed, CSB supported them with 1kg of indigenous variety of Maskalai dal seed. The seed was sown in a fallow piece of land where they hardly used to use it for any cultivation. At the time of harvest the one kg seed had produced 60 kg of dal and which was fully organic. The neighbors got attracted as they could feel the quality of the of the dal produced was of good color and crispy.

Organic produce is good at taste, boils easily, smells great, chemical free and is healthy. This created a demand for the seed among the neighbors for self-consumption and even for sale. The quality of the maskalai dal was so good that they need not to travel to market for sale. Per kg dal was sold at Rs. 150 / kg which is standard price in the retail market for the same. It was always that the farmers whenever sale to wholesaler or middle man used to get almost half of the market price. But in this case, it was opposite.

Out of the 60 kg of total produce they returned 4 kg of dal to seed bank and rest 20 kg was kept for self-consumption and the 37.5 kg were sold at Rs. 150 /kg, i.e., she earned Rs. 5625.00 from a fallow piece of land.

The neighboring farmers are now very much interested to grow the same crop and eager to get attached with CSB and take other facility from the bank.

Other aspect of CSB

Timing in agriculture is the crux of profitable factor in agriculture. Good quality seed and perfect window of sowing leads to development of a crop. Apart from quality seed support from CSB at the right time and at the right place as per demand of the farmers the seed is being provided at the homestead. Almost like home delivery service. In our case Kamini was benefited specially during covid, where she did not have the headache of searching a shop and get a quality seed and other inputs for the same crop. In the words of Kamini "I did not have to spend money for purchasing the seeds, more over a quality seed and an authentic indigenous seed and that too at our home stead". Apart from seed they provided technical know-how to grow the same crop.

Kamini out of laughter noted "my harvest is purely organic which is now high in demand. Moreover, my cost of production is almost nil as I used my own country plough for tilling the land and used my own cow's cow dung as fertilizer. Finally, my neighbor compliment for tasty dal and urge for feast at week end"

"I for now getting the taste that the demand for local, organic and without chemical produce is always high even in our local market place. If the same organic be sold at slightly high price I could earn better profit out of the same piece of land where previously I used to make loss or high production cost. I will for now keep a separate patch of plot only for organic, indigenous verity crop that would fetch me a good return on investment. I also want to become a known name in my local market due to my organic and tasty produce." Kamini oraon.

"CSB has elaborated the harmful effect of the chemical used in our field and its effect on our family members and the children. The best part of CSB is that they not just provide seed but also provide the guideline to manage the crop. We have learned the importance of seed treatment and that too with trichoderma. Before this we never ever knew about seed treatment and due to which we used to face high mortality and finally less produce. Moreover, for any kind of pest or insect attack we now use neem oil. The main part of agriculture is always less cost of production. And CSB is providing a ray of path towards that direction "as reflected by brother of Kamini, Mithun Oraon

Linkage with other line department

Mithun Oraon addes that very likely we could realize that after getting involved into CSB community, we are getting frequent visit from ADA office like KPS visiting on a regular basis moreover staffs from ATMA are also visiting our place. They are also extending support for any kind of agriculture advise.

Spreading experience

"We both brother and sister now share our knowledge learned from CSB, line department specially on produce of organic crops and management to deal with adversities with the crop. We always excitedly jump in to demonstrate the seed treatment process with water, salt and trichoderma. Moreover, we both emphasize that more farmers involve in farming even after kharif so that animal grazing and bird attack get diminish and we farmers earn more form organic produce." Mithun and Kamin Oraon adds.

“I perceive that if we keep on applying chemical input in the agriculture field than in near future in coming 10 years, we resident of north Bengal have to cutoff 2 feet of top soil and then again have to resume agriculture”, a special message from Mithun Oraon for entire farming fraternity.

The production and new system of CSB has attracted neighboring farmers of the village. farmers like Rina Oraon taken 2 kg black gram from CSB to produce 10 kg of which 2 kg were returned to bank CSB. Esraful Islam is also one of such farmers who was provided 2 kg black gram who produced 25 kg of which 2 kg returned to Bank. Amal Oraon, Binod Oraon was also attracted by the service of CSB and produced almost 5 kg arahar lentil from 250 g seed. They also returned 1 kg of produce to CSB. Slowly but steadily farmers are joining CSB and taking the service of the same. Farmers from different corner of the village are taking information about the CSB

Expectation from CSB

As more farmers will get involve with CSB the quality of seed not to diminish and when organic produce would be more, we farmers won't have to think about marketing. It would be great if we could sale all our produce through this CSB.

Community Seed bank- a boon for tribal farmer

Introduction

Chome Oraon, an old but energetic farmer found ploughing at his farm land with his own country plough early in the morning. The farm land is bounded with a scenic natural beauty flashing a background with elongate blue-sky bleach with greenish blue mountain at distance hugged with drown forest with new leaves and flowers of autumn.

For a break in between his ploughing and reenergizing himself with his home-made energy tonic he made a window to have a discussion with us.

Pic 1: Chome Oraon at his land

Background

Chome oraoon as he says a bit confused about his age but during his school days teacher would make an approximation of the age and according to that he is 63 and the same is reflected in his Adhar and voter card. With this he gives an overwhelming open-heart smile.

He is guardian to 10 members in his house. Agriculture and unskilled labour work is the only source of income for his family. On being asked since when he was engaged with agriculture. to this he proudly revels he is a farmer by profession and feels proud to be called as a farmer. Since his childhood days he used to support his father in farming activity in their forefather agriculture land. Chome proudly announced that, he inherited 8 bigha / 1.07 ha of land from his forefather and still now he is continuing on the same.

What were the crops grown in his field? Along with his father he reminds, that *“those were the days when we never depended on others for farming. We used to have our own seed at our house and we used to sow according to our will. We had our own cattle and the dung were used at manure. The same cattle used for ploughing.*

During kharif season we used to sow paddy variety which you might have never heard of. Did you hear about Dudhkolom variety, bochi variety, kalo nunia? All those we used for preparation of either desert or staffed rice. During pre- kharif we used to go for “desi jute”, which was initially used for self-consumption or some time sale as green leafy vegetable and later sold as jute. And during rabi season we used to go for mustard and that too of desi variety called barin.”

Do you still continue with those variety and crops in your plots? Chome with a deep breath, *“No, I do not grow those variety now. No one wants to purchase those. Whenever I used to take those to market consumers were getting less in past few years as they were attracted to bigger and fresh-looking products. In case of paddy, mine one was not so shiny thus people started to neglect my product which led me to loss for more than a decade. Since then, I stopped producing the desi variety.*

Moreover, management of my desi variety needed keen eye every day, as part of management of the crop. As because we did not have any medicine as of today. In case of any pest or insect attack we physically had to pluck the portion of affected plant and dump in dig beside our plot. Additionally, the paddy variety like dudhkolom and bochi gets affected with wind and finally the production gets affected. Hardly I would get 5 – 6 mon per bigha of production.”

So, what is your present engagement in the farmland? Chome speaks, *“Let me revel you that, now I do own 7 bigha / 0.93 ha of agriculture land. As I discussed previously, I used to support my father in his farming, the same way I take support of my family members as and when require just like during sowing of paddy, harvesting of paddy, jute harvest, jute rating etc. most of the time it’s me who take all the initiative of agriculture planning. My family members including son they do not take any headache of taking any decision regarding the crop / variety / know how choice. So, its fully me who is 100 % engaged with farming. but I am not complaining about my family, as I told as and when require they support me”*

With a pause he exclaimed and charged a question towards us, Chome with a loud voice *“What do you think, agriculture is profitable! no not at all.”* Immediately I countered, *“Why? why do you think so?”*

Twist

Do you know why I own 7 bigha of land now as because I have already sold 1 bigha of land. Its only due to open grazing, bird attack and loss in agriculture. Agriculture now a days becoming costly. Moreover, I need to depend on others for my agriculture. Finding loss in home preserved seed, now I go for shop seeds which produce more production and thus I am getting depended on the shop for the management for the same. As they suggest for many chemical inputs but I don't go for all, as its costly and second it may damage my land.

I do use DAP, 10:26:26 and urea in my field. Whenever I used insecticide or pesticide, I discovered that the attack of pest or insect increase next year, and thus now I do not use the same. And more over if I keep on applying spray and other chemical, it will become a habit and I may not resist myself from applying the same. This in lieu will increase my cost of production, though get high rate of production.

What do you produce in your farmland now? For now, during kharif I grow hybrid variety paddy like Sourav, Hairas variety that produce almost like 15 – 16 mon per bigha. During pre-kharif I go with Jute with Torsha variety where I apply DAP and phosphate as chemical input. During Rabi season I now go with tomato, cabbage, green leafy vegetable, chili and Okra. This year I have already sold cabbage, tomato okra in market and rest were unsold.

Challenges faced

But I should mention though production is on higher side due to hybrid variety and chemical input but still there are many problems I face in agriculture. The very first thing I must mention is that farming is getting costlier day by day and on the hinge side our dependency on fertilizer shop is getting overrating. Previously we were depended on rain for better crop but now we are depended on either agriculture department or other department and fertilizer input shop for the same.

it was only during covid scenario when we realized that how much we creeped dependency on others. But during covid scenario it was only CSB who was by my side to support in agriculture aspect.

The land Chome oraon poses categorized as "Dola" i.e., low land. In case of heavy rain there is a chance of crop damage. In the meantime, in last one decade the farmers of the place have received irrigation facility along with dug well from govt. line department. But the fate of the physical infrastructures on present date is defunct.

Chome is under deep thought that how he could develop his situation to earn profit out of his scenario. On the other hand, Chobe is smart enough to stick to his basics, i.e., plowing and tilling his land with his own country plough and preserving few of his indigenous variety like okra, mustard, chili and jute at his home stead. He grows green leafy vegetable and other seasonal crop for his own consumption so that he need not to spend cash on purchasing the same from market.

But he is much more concern that as he is a professional farmer so what and how and which crop will fetch him more money.

CSB

On the role of Community Seed Bank Chome was very precise. He indicated that, "I am lucky to be part of such community. During covid 19 when none of the shop were open for us to purchase inputs. None of the line department were for us it was CSB who came up with initial support. It was CSB who supported with 1 kg mustard seed which I sow over 2 bigha of land. But the sad part due to rain and water log for a day my crop was damaged. But I could get 40 kg of produce at the end of the

season. But I am not dishearten only because the seed variety provided to me was one of our indigenous varieties. Thus, I am confirming that by next year I will preserve seed to produce more in same path of land. More over through CSB I would have a backup for my seed as I have deposited 2.5 kg of seed in the bank.

Apart from Mustard they provided lentil (moosor) which I cultivated through “Poyra” technique in 1 bigha land. I could generate almost 8 kg of moosor dal from that 1 bigha land. I am very much excited that for the first time I harvested lentil in my land and that too for CSB.

CSB not only provided seed for cultivation but technique, management and hand hold support to manage the crops.” Chome again added, the most important component he learned through CSB was seed treatment. He never used to treat his seed but now that is done organically and results in less mortality.

Another aspect which added my skill in to recognition that the procedure to preserve the desi seeds. Traditionally Chome used to preserve the seed by sun dry and then storing in cotton cloth.

I would sale few of my mustard oil in market at Rs. 2.50 per kilo. Just to check if my oil has demand. If I could sale at same price then from next year, I would do whatever it takes to manage the crop and harvest a higher productivity.

Farmers all-round the village are taking support of Chome and thus attracting towards the service of CSB. Farmers like Tej Bahadur Sonar, Subhalaxmi Roy, Dhaleshrai Roy, Sankar Roy, Anita Das is getting motivated and few of them have already received seed like mustard and lenti. More of the farmers are now inquisitive to get service of CSB in near future.

Call of heart

Chome while concluding his note suggested few points for CSB. Which goes like

- a. CSB is a boon for farmers like us who have not completely shifted to chemical farming but honor our traditional farming. CSB is supporting to revive those seed which are on verge of extinct.
- b. CSB promotes preserving of indigenous seed variety as we traditional practice for few many seeds. This would encourage us to preserve our heritage and cultural farming.
- c. I personally feel proud that I am still not backdated as bracketed by young generation who are fully inclined to modern, chemical and hybrid technique of agriculture.
- d. But I just cannot depend only on indigenous variety. I am a farmer, be it organic or non-organic, be it chemical or chemical free I will have to choose those crop and variety which would fetch me money. Hence, if CSB apart from pulses seed prove us some seeds of vegetable which would fetch me money in long patch of time includes chilly, cabbage seeds.

A female farmers dream

Name of the farmer – Anita Roy Age – 43 Category – SC
Educational qualification – X Village- Uttar Dhupjhora
Family members – 4
Profession – home maker, shopkeeper but a full-time farmer.
Agriculture experience – 25 years (approx.) Agriculture land – 3.5 bigha
Support – Family specially husband

Livestock – Cattle and goat. Cattle for milk, goat for sale.

Anita Roy, a middle-aged woman belonging from Uttar Dhupjhora village runs her family through agriculture and various allied works. At her father's house she hardly engaged in agriculture works as her father was a service holder but had one bigha of land which was utilized as kitchen garden. That was her touch with agriculture until she was married to a farming family. Her husband Noni Roy was farmer. The family poses 3.5 bigha / ... acre of agriculture land where they used to crop Paddy during Kharif, Jute during Pre-kharif and almost fallow during Rabi. 1 bigha of land is engaged with tea plantation.

Typically, as other families they also used their traditional paddy variety like Payjam, Dudhklom, Kalonuniya. But the production of those variety ranged between 6- 7 mon per bigha. Hardly they could fetch good return as they a good portion had to be kept for own consumption and rest were sold. But as production was less in limited land, they were always in search of variety which would fetch higher production to churn high profit.

The entire family is farming dependent. Thus, they were highly concern of production with the limited amount of land possessed. The jute they produce also do not fetch high yield. Its only like 2.5 mon / 100 kg jute extracted from .5 bigha of land.

Pic 1: Anita Roy with his husband Noni Roy

Challenge

Just before Covid 19 her husband due an accident faced a fanatic issue in his leg and thus pushing physical work to a backstage. Though he is fine worth walking and other daily work but farming needs a better physical effort which he is unable to execute.

On such situation they were bound to take help of tractor for ploughing, daily wage labor for farming activity like transplanting of paddy seedlings, harvesting, harvesting of jute, rating and other activities. All those increased the cost of production of the produce. The situation become more crunch during covid. They were unable to get labour nor inputs for agriculture.

In such situation they were fully depended on the livestock they had i.e., goat and cattle. The problem did not stop there. They even started facing challenge in irrigating their crop field. Though there are facility of irrigation in the fields provided from government line department but are not adequate to serve the number of farmers engaged in the same patch of field they were installed for.

Moreover, as their farm plots lies near the forest there are threats of elephant and other animal to destroy crops specially the banana, maize, paddy. apart from animals' birds also flock on the crops and destroys a lot.

On the other side due to construction of resorts at the fringe of forest have hindered the natural water that used to flow towards their plots from forest. All these issues collectively led them to a dent or crisis in agriculture.

Alternative initiative

To get rid of the crisis situation she tried her hands on few many aspects. Being member of SHG she was trained on vermicomposting. they ventured compost with 2 pits where they produced vermicompost but faced problem in marketing. A limited quantity of the produce was sold but lion share of the produce had to utilize in their own farmland. Moreover, due to scarcity of earth worm the venture has stopped.

Apart from regular crop she initiated some vegetable like bottle gourd, pumpkin, lafa (green leafy) for self-consumption and for sale. She earned a good amount from these crops.

She again ventured a small shop in her house to run some daily expenses for last few months.

A ray of hope

Struggling on given situation, Anita somehow learned about Community Seed Bank (CSB). She hunched for the office and could finally get in touch with CSB. As per assistance the CSB for the first time assisted her with arahar dal (lentil). They were suggested to use the same at their existing tea plantation plot as that would act as shed tree and second, they can utilize the same plot.

CSB support

Name of seed	Variety	Quantity provided	Area	Production	Remarks	Other assistance provided
Arahar	Indigenous	500g	Inter cropping with tea plants	11 kg	Expected 40 kg, fruiting was great but bird attack. But 3	Training on crop management
Tishi	Indigenous	2 kg	1 bigha	Running	Expect good	Training on

				crop	production. Attempting for the first time.	crop management
Til	Indigenous	1 kg	1 bigha	Nil	Due to early sowing, seeds did not germinate	
Moosor lentil	Indigenous	3 kg	10 katha	Nil	Destroyed due to lack of irrigation	

In the words of Anita, “CSB has extended its support during my crisis period. Generally, we used to keep our land fallow after kharif paddy as we had no adequate source of water for irrigation. They provided free of cost seeds that too according to our need and situation. The most important part was timely support and home delivery service. In agriculture timing is very important and that was the key word learned through CSB. More over the tension of finding quality seed has diminished as becoming part of CSB. Apart from this support another important skill learned from CSB was seed preservation. Though I used to preserve few of the seeds like pumpkin and chilli. The staff of CSB trained me the correct way to preserve our seeds for next year. This process was interesting and helpful. At least I would not to purchase few of the seeds from market in cash now. So, cost of production will be diminished”.

Ye dil mange more!

As per Anita and her husband, “The support CSB is providing in our village is tremendous. the small initiative can evolve as bigger venture. I just think of this bank as a unique bank. Just as Bandhan bank evolved from microfinance to a nationalized bank in less than 20 years, we also dream that our CSB would also evolve on same strata once in coming years. The “seed bank passbook” gives us the confidence that this has the potential to take those strata.”

In this village farmers are getting attracted towards the service of CSB. Farmers like Rekha Roy, Dipti Roy, Saraswati Roy is getting interested in receiving services of CSB. Few of the farmers have already received seeds like khesari, mustard and blackgram.

There are few more expectation from CSB for their customer like

- As females after work in afternoon has no work to do but only chitchat, CSB can provide some skill or work to engage.
- CSB can engage the SHG in some activity
- CSB can provide training on activity regarding its operations
- Apart from pulse seed CSB need to work on other seeds.

CSB- farmers friend indeed

“To forget how to dig the earth and to tend the soil is to forget ourselves”, Mahatma Gandhi.

The living story of a common man who stick to basic for its own livelihood, a farmer who never ever in life, dosed chemical to churn high yield from crops in his farmland. Jitu Lohar a tribal old man aged 62 precise is a farmer first and simultaneously a proud father of two son who are deployed to Indian Army for several years.

This humble noble person before self-introduction, proudly introduce her wife as her life partner in sense. In the word of Jittu, “Before we begin our conversation as a farmer, I must introduce my wife who is at par partner with me in every sect of my farming journey.”

Jitu Lohar was 2nd number son of his father. Before marriage he was with his father at Batabari farm which is 6 Km from his present residence. After marriage, almost 30 years back, he found the necessity to earn and nurture his family. As per his analysis, as he was just class 5 pass and had no professional skill, he decided to take on farming as his profession and source of livelihood. In the word of Lohar, “Being child I always used to help my father in farming”. He inherited 1 bigha / .33 ha units of land from his father and to indulge in farming he shifted with family to his present residence at Uttor Dhupjhora.

Pic 1: Jitu Lohar with his wife at her residence

Lohar, "Presently I grow okra, brinjal, chilli and basella in my land and directly sell it to local market." with a shy and soft smile he proclaims that when ever he takes his produce to market, almost all the customers jump in to purchase my product. Lohar, "We both husband and wife go to market to sell our product. Whatever we produce load it in a cycle then along with my wife I paddle to the local market either at Dhupjhora market or Mangalbari market. My wife books a separate stall and me the other. Whenever there is need, we are both there for each other. Moreover, if stock at my stall sells out then product from other stall is again reloaded to make a quick sale. Its very rare that we have to return our produce from market unsold." Lohar continues, "Do you know, the magic of my produce is only due to my livestock and love for the crops I grow. The produce is also demanding because they get a motherly care from my wife".

Lohar has cow, goat, hen and duck at his backyard nurtured by him and his family. Presently he is guardian to 10 members in the family. All his family members collectively perform all the task regarding nurturing the livestock, crop management in the field and other daily task in the farmland. Never ever they hire labour for their agriculture work.

On asking what is so specialty of your produce that its sales like a hot cake, Lohar explains that he only uses his cattle dung as fertilizer. More over the dung of different livestock is used for different crop. Like goat dung is good for Rai sag (green leafy vegetable) crop and in general cow dung is good for other crops. its my experience of last 30 years that has helped him to gain this reputation. According to Lohar, "farming is a skill one has to observe, nurture and perceive what each crop speaks. As our human body goes through various diseases so does the plants. Being tribal genie, we hardly take support of allopathic treatment for our body. For minor diseases we take support of plants and herbs available at our vicinity. Likewise, I do learn what is the problem of the crop and likewise apply medicine and that too natural remedies. Finally, the produce which is consumed by our customer gets cooked quickly, boils easily, taste great with a natural aroma in the recipe. This in lieu gets me repeat customer and demand for the same gets high."

Until now it may sound great, but is it always he is graced with such a good produce and fair market. no, its not the case. But in compare to the hybrid produce specially in case of vegetables and green leafy vegetables the local indigenous variety gets less damage in shorter period. In one say the produced can be termed as "Organic". To register such strata in market the farmer had undergo several challenges in last 2-3 decade which still continues.

Farming tale and Lohar

With a limited amount of land inherited from his father as he initiated agriculture as profession, crossed 30 long years. By now he won 2.5 bigha / .33 ha unit of land. But the journey as a farmer was not so easy. Apart from his farmland there were large patch of farmland owned by other farmers along Lohars land. General practice of other farmers was after kharif paddy the lands were kept fallow but Lohar never used to keep his land fallow. And there lies the issue, open cattle grazing. Though he never refrained from planting seasonal and off-season crop.

In the words of Lohar, "Me being a farmer is my duty to produce crop and challenges go hand in hand. If I had to choose some other profession there might also be challenge. And it is nature, whatever is good gets attracted by others. In my case, cattle, birds, wild animal and sometime insect / pest gets attracted to my crop. And here lies the management which includes monitoring as a crucial part. I just cannot decentralize my work and relax. It is always when I need to be engaged with them. But it is not possible for us always to be with crops in field, so we have some auto-pilot mode. That is, we put bio- haze camouflaged with border to get rid of cattle and wild animals, bio-

pesticide / insecticide on the plants to get rid of insect and pest, glazy tape round the crops to get rid of birds. But the only hindrance we cannot plot is for elephant. He is our lord.”

What kind of crops is grown in your plots, to this Lohar brings a trail of his land from very beginning. According to Lohar,” very initial stages almost 30 years ago and years later I used to grow paddy whose name you might have never heard of. I used to grow ‘Mala’ for puffed rice, ‘Garua dhepi’ for staffed rice, ‘Dudhkolom’ for puffed rice, ‘Tulaipanji’ for Desert like payesh, ‘Jharial’ for puffed rice, ‘Payjam’ for rice. These were the paddy variety. During pre-kharif jute of ‘desi’ variety, the red one specially as green leafy vegetable. ‘Suti’ and ‘Torsha’ variety was for jute.”

Lohar continues, “In agriculture timing is very important. (With a laugh) As in cricket hitting a ball for six is all matter of timing for a batsman, just for a farmer timing the seed sowing is very important. In case of jute, as farmer one can make profit in two ways one by saleing the plants as green leafy vegetable during early season like late February or early March the other way is saleing as jute but what makes difference is the colour and texture of the Jute. The trick to get quality jute is timing of harvesting and then retting in running water.”

But slowly the use of old seeds specially for paddy has diminished only because of its production. As compared to old variety seeds as discussed above the new variety like Jamuna, Surav , Sarna produce almost double in same pathch of land and with almost same cost of production. This is why they have now shifted to new variety of paddy. to be precise the old variety produce like 7-8 mon per bigha where as new variety produce 20 – 22 mon per bigha. Hence after utilizing for home consumption the produce could be sold where as previously the produce was enough for own consumption. As per Lohar, for paddy he cultivates 12 bigha from where on average he produces 18 mon / 720 kg per bigha. The produce is sold from his home @ Rs. 500 / mon.

Challenge

Previously Lohar had a good storage of indigenous variety of seed for various crops but as time passed, he has very limited variety. Still, he has a process to preserve the same. sundry every ten to twelve days in a plate of coconut branch and then again store in plastic in a dry and cool place in room. Now he has to purchase seeds from market for most of the crop. And there lies the biggest constraint.

As of an experienced farmer he knows, how much timing is important to earn high range of profit from same crop in same path of land but in a different way. Like during Durga puja he targets to bring green leafy vegetable in market which earns huge profit as its in high demand with less effort. Likewise, during march demand for okra, long yard bean, bitter gourd is very high. But the problem he faces every year is the quality of seed purchased from market is very bad. Unknowingly the farmers are cheated and finally deprived from earning profit.

Friend in need

In the words of Lohar, “Do you know, now we have a bank at our village who is keeping eye on farmers biggest challenge and that is seed. They provide best quality, climate friendly and more importantly our indigenous variety. The bank provide seed as per farmers need and demand, in lieu after produce we need to return them 2.5 times the seed supported by the bank. This is such a unique and timely support system for the farmers that a farmer can understand.”

Added by other family members of Lohar that the CSB has supported them during utmost need of time during the covid scenario. Being a farmer family, they were tired of being cheated for bad quality seed whereas the labour time they invested resulted to loss. The facial expression of the

family members and Lohar himself changed discussing about CSB and its benefit. They were happy to share their experience with CSB.

As Loghar continues “Last season during Rabi 2021-22 I received pea seeds from CSB which I planted in my desi potato plot. Both of my plant growth was very good but to some extent the produce was damaged by rodent. But still I could harvest a quality pea and used for self-consumption and few were sold in the market. apart from pea I received pulse seed like Moong, kalai dal, Arahara, Khesari, Sunflower and mustard. Let me tell you an interesting fact about the indigenous variety of seeds is that the production is very less compared to hybrid but tastes great and again can be reused for more than 10 years if preserved in correct way where as in case of hybrid seed, we need to purchase every year.”

CSB support

Name of seed	Variety	Quantity provided	Area	Production	Remarks	Other assistance provided
Mustard	Indigenous	500 g	10 katha / .07 ha	15 kg	Produced 4.5 liter of mustard oil	Training on crop management
Kolai dal	Indigenous	1 kg	10 katha / .07 ha	20 kg	Expect good production. But bird attack.	Training on crop management
Sunflower	Indigenous	250 g	1 Katha / .01 ha	Destroyed by bird	Could not harvest	Hand hold training
Arahara	Indigenous	250 g	5 katha / .03 ha	Nil	Accidentally weeded by minor member of family	
Khesari	indigenous	3 kg	1 bigha / .13 ha	Nil	Destroyed by bird	
Moosor	indigenous	3 kg	1 bigha / .13 ha	Nil	Destroyed by bird	
Pea	indigenous	1 kg	Inter cropping with potato	5 kg		

CSB is playing a significant role in the life of farmers of that village. Apart from seed distribution also focus on crop management and suggest know how to farmers to go on with the variety. Now farmers are stressless in case of finding a quality seed and at the time when it is needed. The biggest factor is to find a quality seed free of cost as when require even if farmer face challenge with no money. Most of the time in village like these, farmers till their land with country plough that ensure no cash involvement and the fertilizer is generally the dung of the livestock. Hence the cash involvement was the seed which now ensured by CSB specially in pulse category.

In the words of Lohar, “Previously I used to grow pulses like arahara, moosor in my plots but as due to unavailability of quality seed I stopped growing the same for last 10 years. Now only due to CSB I could resume growing pulses. Though I am facing whole lot of problem like threat of birds eating the

to-be -ripe fruits of sunflower, arahar, Khesari, but still, I want to continue with the crops. I won't get dishearten, rather pump up my neighbor farmers to grow same in their fields. As few many farmers are showing interest for next year. As I could see the difference in my plots that the leguminous plats of pulse category grown in my paddy field showing sign of improved fertility.”

CSB effect

Lohar and his family members reflect that its only due to CSB they have again initiated to preserve seed in their traditional way since last year. Now they are relief that if their own seed gets destroyed or crop affect for any given reason, they have a backup in the seed bank.

Previously another important aspect was never performed by Lohar is seed treatment. Now only training through CSB they are treating seeds with Tricoderma.

Availability of seed at homestead is another important aspect, previously had to travel minimum 5 km to purchase any seed this has diminish the cost of production of farmer. More over as the produce is organic there are frequent visit of middleman to purchase the produce from house. If farmers calculate they are profitable like for example Kalai dal (Lentil) sold by Lohar from his house was Rs. 140 / kg where as in retail market the same is sold at Rs. 150 / kg.

Lohar proudly shares those farmers like Deepak Oraon who is friend of mine and shares just his immediate plot of land are initiating crops like mustard, black gram taking support of CSB. Lohar motivated other farmers to be part of such opportunity at the doorstep. Farmers like Ashok Oraon, Kaliprassana Roy are also initiating mustard as part of CSB service.

Last effective words and suggestion for CSB from Lohar was that, it would be great if the quality and timing through CSB be persistence no factor in this world would stop leading the flourishing of CSB in our state in bigger way. He perceives one day when many farmers would produce indigenous variety then big trucks would be visiting the village to take the produce to outside state and even in our state capital. The CSB should also think of tracking of skillful farmers who can in future became the hands of CSB to upscale the reach of CSB's mission and vision.
